

JOB PROMOTION AS A PREDICTOR OF TEACHERS' PRODUCTIVITY IN SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN NORTH-EAST, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study investigated the level to which teachers job promotion could predict teachers' job productivity in Senior Secondary Schools in North-East, Nigeria. One research question was answered and one hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted a correlational survey research design. The population for the study was 22, 733 subjects which comprised of 965 principals and 21, 768 teachers from Senior Secondary Schools in six states (Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba and Yobe) drawn from North-East, Nigeria. Multistage sampling technique was used in selecting the sample for the study. Four states were purposively drawn for the study because of insurgency. These are Adamawa, Bauchi, Gombe and Yobe. 50% of educational zones from each of the selected states for the study was applied. Random sampling technique was used in selecting the educational zones from the states selected for the study. The sample size for the study was 1, 221 subjects which comprised 225 principals and 996 teachers. Teachers' Job Promotion Questionnaire was developed by the researcher from the review of literature and a 12 item Structured Questionnaire titled "Teachers' Productivity Questionnaire" was adopted from Ayeni (2020). The instruments were face-validated by 8 experts in the school of education in Modibbo Adama University, Yola. In order to determine the reliability of the instruments, the test-retest method was used to collect data from respondents outside the study area and data collected were analysed using the Cronbach Alpha Method. The results of the test yielded reliability indices of 0.856 and 0.811 for the Teachers Job Promotion Questionnaire and Teachers' Productivity Questionnaire respectively. The data relating to research question were analysed using descriptive statistics of mean of standard deviation while linear regression was used in analysing data relating to hypothesis which was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study showed, among others, that the level of teachers' job promotion is high and that teachers job promotion is a significant predictor of teachers' productivity in Senior Secondary Schools in North East, Nigeria. It was recommended that even thou teachers job promotion is high principals and Government should not relent in regularizing teachers' promotion as that will prevent them from looking for other jobs.

Keywords: Job Promotion, Predictor, Teachers' Productivity

Introduction

Productivity is the ratio between the volume of output and the volume of input and it implies an efficient utilization of available resources in achieving a pre-determined goal. Productivity is important in all sectors of the economy especially in the education sector. Thus, the stake holders at all levels of education (primary, secondary and universities) are deeply interested in the quality of teachers' productivity. Tijani (2015) opined that productivity is a measure of how well resources

such as information, finance, human and physical resources are combined and utilized to accomplish specific and desirable result. Productivity may therefore, be regarded as the relationship between output and associated inputs measured in real terms.

Getange (2016) opined that teachers' productivity could be described as the duties performed by a teacher at a particular period in the school system geared towards achieving a desired goal. It could also be described as the ability of teachers to combine relevant inputs for enhancement of the teaching – learning process. However, productivity on the part of teachers is determined by their level of participation in the day to day running of the school; regularity in school and class attendance, and students' level of discipline as well as proper use of instructional materials to facilitate learning. Getange further asserted that variables of teachers' productivity such as effective teaching, lesson note preparation, effective use of scheme of work, effective supervision, monitory of student's work and disciplinary ability are virtues which teachers should uphold effectively in a school system.

Teachers' productivity can be enhanced through recognition, reward and job promotion. Saharuddin and Sulaiman (2016) stated that promotion is evidence of recognition of employee performance. Promotion is very important to the company because it assures the stability of the company and boosts employee morale. Most teachers like to be recognized openly and be given posts. The aim of every teacher is to be promoted, be given higher responsibility as no teacher would like to experience denial of promotion, poor image and negligence.

In the context of this work, promotion can also be described as higher-level job title, increase in status and more administrative powers, increased duties, evidence of recognition of teacher's performance, enhancement of right and increased incentives of teachers. Mwijage (2015) stated that promotion is the advancement of an employee from one job position to another job position that has higher salary range, a higher-level job title, and often; more and higher-level job responsibilities. It is also an upward movement of an employee in an organization's hierarchy.

Khaliq (2021) carried out a study to investigate the effect of salary, promotion, and relationships with colleagues on teachers' job satisfaction at public sector secondary schools of the district Faisalabad, Punjab, Pakistan. The results revealed that salary, promotion and relationships with colleagues have significant effect on teachers' job satisfaction. Chukwu and Ezepe (2018) saw promotion as a motivational instrument for effective workforce performance and retention. Promotion is upward movement based on years of experience, qualification and achievement. Teachers' promotion is growth and advancement in a cadre or rank with its financial benefit and recognition. Regulation promotion is likely to motivate teachers to be more productive and effective.

Igbogi (2018) carried out a study on teachers' welfare and commitment as determinants of productivity in secondary schools in Bayelsa State. The study revealed that effective organization/management, staff training, good financial benefits and regular promotion influenced productivity. Baba Ibi, Gwary and Adamu (2020) carried out a study to determine the correlate of conditions of service and teachers' productivity in secondary schools in Maiduguri metropolis, Borno State, Nigeria. The variables under study include teachers' pay-package, teachers' working environment, teachers' fringe benefits, teachers' promotion and teachers' job security in Maiduguri metropolis. The results of the study revealed that there was no significant relationship between pay-package and teachers' productivity, no significant relationship between working environment and teachers' productivity, there was a significant relationship between fringe benefits and teachers' productivity, there was no significant relationship between implementation of promotion and teachers' productivity and there was no significant relationship between job security and teacher' productivity in Maiduguri

metropolis secondary schools. Saharuddin and Sulaiman (2016) carried out a study on the effect of promotion and compensation on work productivity through job satisfaction and working motivation of employees in the Department of Water and Mineral Resources Energy, North Aceh District of Indonesia. Their study examined job satisfaction and morale as a mediator of the relationship between promotion and compensation with productivity as well as reviewing the moderating effect of job satisfaction and moral variables. It was concluded that promotion, compensation, job satisfaction and morale simultaneously have significant effect on the productivity of workers. Ndiujye and Tandika (2019) explained that timely promoted teachers have positive impact on pupils' learning progress because those who are not promoted put very little efforts in the teaching. Sometimes, pupils are left alone in the classroom the whole day without learning anything. From the foregoing discussion, it can be said that lack of promotion among teachers or not being promoted as at when due makes teachers not to put in their best and this may likely affect their productivity. The problem of this study is that the level of promotion of secondary school teachers in North-East, Nigeria and the extent to which it affects their productivity at work is not known.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the level to which job promotions could predict teachers' productivity in Senior Secondary Schools in North-East, Nigeria.

Research Question

The research question is "What is the level of prediction of teacher's productivity by teachers' job promotion in Senior Secondary Schools in North East, Nigeria?"

Hypothesis

H₀₁: Teachers' job promotion does not significantly predict their productivity in Senior Secondary Schools in North East, Nigeria.

Methodology

Research Design

Correlational research design was adopted for this study. According to Ary, Jacobs, Razavieh and Sorensen (2006), correlational research design is most useful for determining relationships, assessing consistency and prediction. Correlational research design is suitable for this study because in this study, data on independent variable i.e. teachers' job promotion and dependent variable i.e. teachers' productivity were collected and correlated. The extent to which the independent variable (s) predicted the dependent variable were determined.

Area of the Study

The study was conducted in Senior Secondary Schools in North-East, Nigeria (Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba and Yobe)

Population for the Study

The population for the study is a total of 22,733. Subjects which comprise of 965 principals and 21, 768 teachers in senior secondary schools in North-East, Nigeria i.e. Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba and Yobe States respectively. The distribution of the numbers of principals and teachers in senior secondary schools in their respective states as shown in table 1.

Table 1: Population Distribution

States	Educational Zones	Principals	Teachers
Adamawa	5	274	5,731
Bauchi	3	214	4,941
Borno	4	32	2,078
Gombe	3	111	2,460
Taraba	10	285	3,393
Yobe	3	49	3,165
Total	28	965	21,768

Sources: post primary schools management Board Yola, Adamawa State, Ministry of Education, Bauchi State, ministry of Education Gombe, Gombe State, Ministry of Education Jalingo, Taraba State, Ministry of Education Maiduguri, Borno State and Ministry of Education Damaturu, yobe State.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The researcher used four out of the six states in North-East, Nigeria selected through purposive sampling due to insurgency. The states are Adamawa, Bauchi, Gombe and Taraba. Multistage sampling technique was used in selecting the sample for the study (principals and teachers) from the educational zones in the four states and the researcher selected 50% of education zones in each of the states as follows: Adamawa-3, Bauchi-2, Gombe-2 and Taraba-5. Simple random sampling technique was used in selecting the education zones from the selected states. Nwanna (2005) parameter was applied in selecting the sample size for the study. According to Nwanna (Ibid), if the population of the study is a few hundreds, 40% or more sample size will do; if many hundreds, 20% will do; if a few hundreds, 10% sample size will do, and if several thousands, 5% or less will do. To select the sample size of principals, 20% was applied and the following were obtained; 40% of 156=62 for Adamawa, 40% of 16=64 for Bauchi, 40% of 71=28 for Gombe and 40% of 177=71 for Taraba, making a total of 225 principals. In selecting the sample size for teachers, 10% was used with the exception of Bauchi state which 5% was applied because the number is more and is several thousands. For Adamawa state, 10% of 3,701 is 370, for Bauchi state, 5% of 4,025 is 201, for Gombe state, 10% of 1,805, is 181, for Taraba state, 10% 2,439 is 244. This gave a total of 996. Therefore, the sample size for the study is 1221 subjects: 225 for principals and 996 for teachers.

Instruments for Data Collection

The instruments that were used for data collection in this study were; a 10-item structured questionnaire for teachers titled Job promotion and a 12-item structured questionnaire for principals titled “Teachers Productivity Questionnaire”. The Job Promotion Questionnaire was constructed by the researcher after a thorough review of literature and teachers’ productivity questionnaire was adopted from Ayeni (2020).

The items on both instruments were placed on a 5-point rating scale. Respondents were required to tick the options which best describes their opinions as follows;

- Very High Level (VHL) 5 points
- High Level (HL) 4 points
- Moderate Level (ML) 3 points
- Low Level (LL) 2 points
- Very Low Level (VLL) 1 point

Validation of the Instruments

Eight experts from the faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University(MAU), Yola, face-validated the instruments. Four of the experts were from Physical Sciences Education Department, one from Technology Education Department, and three from Life and Environmental Science Education Department. They were given the title of the study, the research questions and the hypothesis and then request to appraise the content, language, relevance, and adequacy of the instrument to collect data for the purpose of this study. All the suggestions and recommendations from the validations were carefully considered and used in the draft of the final instrument.

Reliability of the Instruments

In order to determine reliability of the instruments 120 copies of the instruments were administered to principals and teachers in twelve secondary schools in South East, Nigeria using test - retest method. Ninety-six copies of the Job Promotion questionnaire were administered to the teachers at two-week intervals while 24 copies of the teachers’ productivity questionnaire were administered to the 12 principals at two-week intervals. To determine the internal consistency of the instrument, the responses of the respondent were subjected to reliability analysis using Cronbach Alpha method. Reliability coefficients of the two instruments were 0.856 for the job promotion questionnaire and 0.811 for the teachers’ productivity questionnaire. Based on these reliability coefficients it was concluded that both instruments have high internal consistency.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected for this study were analyzed using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) Version 23. The data on the research questions were analyzed with the descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation. The real limits of numbers of the responses categories of the five-point rating scale were used to determine the decision point for the means that was used for the research questions.

Response category	Point	Lower Limit	Upper Limit
Very High Level	5	4.5	5.00
High Level	4	3.5	4.49
Moderate Level	3	2.5	3.39
Low Level	2	1.5	2.49
Very Low Level	1	0.5	1.49

In this study, the grand mean score was used to determine the levels of factors in independent variable and dependent variable based on true limits of numbers. Linear regression statistic was used in analyzing the data relating to the hypothesis that were tested at 0.05 level of significance. It was used because the researcher wanted to predict the dependent variables

based on the value of the independent variable. In order to take decision on the hypotheses, if the computed P value is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected, which implies that, job promotion factor contributed significantly in predicting teacher’s productivity. On the order hand, if the computed P-value was greater than 0.05 level of significance, the hypothesis will be upheld.

Results

The results of the data analysis for the study are presented in line with the research question and hypothesis as follows: In order to answer this research, question the data relating to it were collected analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation and the results are presented table 2

Research Question 1: What is the level of teachers’ job promotion in senior secondary schools?

Table 2. Mean and Standard Deviation of Responses on the Level of Teacher’s Job Promotion

S/N	Items	Mean	S. D	Remark
1	Motivating other employees	3.73	1.088	High level
2	Promoting teachers as and when due	3.53	1.155	High level
3	Using time in ranks as a basis of promotion	3.50	1.121	High-level
4	Promoting teachers on the basis of outstanding performance	3.51	1.169	High-level
5	Recognition of employees indiscipline	3.49	1.132	Moderate level
6	Ensuring stability of employment	3.58	1.148	High level
7	Volunteering for additional responsibilities	3.77	1.054	High-level
8	Increase in higher level of job responsibilities	3.67	1.040	High-level
9	Assurance about the continuity of jobs	3.65	.996	High-level
10	Reduction in labor turn over	3.58	1.015	High-level
Grand mean		3.60		High-level

N = 958 (Total number of respondents)

Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation of the respondents on level of teacher’s job promotion. The mean of the ten items on job promotion ranges from 3.49 for “Recognition of employee’s indiscipline” to 3.77 for “Volunteering for additional responsibilities”. The variability of the responses ranges from 0.996 for “Assurance about the continuity of jobs” to 1.169 for “Promoting teachers on the basis of outstanding performance”. The table also shows the grand mean of the items to be 3.60. Based on the above results, both the grand mean and the mean of the individual items are high. Therefore, the level of teacher’s job promotions is high in senior secondary schools in North-East, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Testing

The hypothesis was analysed using linear regression at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: Teacher’s job promotion does not significantly predict their productivity in senior secondary schools in North-East Nigeria

Table 3a: ANOVA Summary Regression Table of Prediction of Teacher’s Job Promotion and Teacher’s Productivity in Senior Secondary Schools in North-East, Nigeria

MODEL	SUM OF SQUARES	DF	MEAN SQUARE	F	SIG
1.Regression	13.798	1	13.798	61.324	.000 ^b
Residual	44.558	198	.225		
TOTAL	58.386	199			

a. Dependent Variable: Level of teacher Productivity

b. Predictors: (Constant) Job promotion

Results of Analysis in Table 3a indicates the summary of ANOVA used to test whether teachers’ job promotion is a significant predictor of teachers’ productivity in Senior Secondary Schools in North East Geo-political zone of Nigeria. The results revealed that teachers’ job promotion is a significant predictor of teachers’ productivity in Senior Secondary Schools in North East of Nigeria, $F(1, 199) = 61.270, p < 0.05$. Since the p – value (0.000) is less than 0.05 alpha level, we conclude that the null hypothesis should be rejected. This means that teachers’ job promotion is a significant predictor of teachers’ productivity in Senior Secondary Schools in North East, Nigeria.

Table 3b: Model Summary Prediction Between Teachers’ Job Promotion and Teachers’ Productivity

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.486 ^a	.236	.232	.47454

a. Predictors: (Constant), Job promotion

The result in Table 3b shows the model summary which indicates how the independent variable explains the variance in the dependent variable. The result shows that the teachers’ job promotion explained 23.2% of the variance in teachers’ productivity in Senior Secondary Schools. Teachers’ job promotion and teachers’ productivity in Senior Secondary Schools were found to have moderate positive relationship which is indicated by r value of 0.486.

Table 3c: Regression Coefficients Prediction Between Teachers’ Job Promotion and Teachers’ Productivity

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.372	.170		13.915	.000
	Job promotion	.366	.047	.486	7.828	.000

a. Dependent Variable: teachers’ productivity

The result in Table 13c indicates the Beta coefficient of the regression analysis of teachers’ job promotion and teachers’ productivity. The result shows a beta coefficient of 0.486, $t = 7.829, p = 0.000, < 0.05$. This indicates that teachers’ job promotion is a significant predictor of teachers’ productivity.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study on teacher’s job promotion as a predictor of teachers’ productivity revealed that teachers’ job promotion significantly predicted teachers’ productivity. The finding is in line with the finding of Khaliq (2021) and was supported with that of Igbogi (2018) and was also supported with that of Sharaddin and Sulaiman (2016). This study disagreed with the findings of Babalbi, Gwary and Adamu (2020) which revealed that there was no significant relationship between pay-package and teachers’ productivity, no significant relationship between working environment and teachers’ productivity, there was a significant relationship between fringe benefits and teachers’ productivity, there was no significant relationship between implementation of promotion and teachers’ productivity and was no significant relationship between job security and teachers’ productivity in Maiduguri metropolis secondary schools.

The finding showed that job promotion has a direct influence on motivating employees, increase in higher level of job responsibilities and assurance about the continuity of their job. Teachers, when promoted, work with concern to promote discipline are more enthusiastic I classroom attendance and even extend to administrative functions. So regular promotions make workers to work hard or be a workaholic, since they know it is always coming but if it is not or there is no sign of that, teachers will not be motivated to work. Both principals and ministries of education are encouraged to regularize teachers’ promotions.

Conclusion

This comprehensive study examined job promotion from various perspectives, including its implications for elevating teachers' status, granting them greater administrative authority, expanding their job responsibilities, recognizing their performance, enhancing their rights, and providing increased incentives. The study's core objective was to investigate whether job promotion could serve as a significant predictor of teacher productivity. The conclusive findings unequivocally establish that job promotion is indeed a pivotal predictor of teacher productivity. It underscores the crucial role job promotion plays in motivating educators, boosting their dedication, and ultimately improving educational outcomes. These insights emphasize the importance of developing promotion systems that reward and acknowledge teachers' efforts, guiding educational institutions and policymakers toward strategies that can retain and inspire highly effective educators, ultimately fostering more successful educational environments. In summary, this study highlights job promotion as a driving force behind increased teacher productivity and the overall success of educational institutions.

Recommendation

On the basis of the finding of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. While it is true that job promotions lead to increased employee satisfaction and enhanced motivation, both school principals and government authorities should maintain a consistent approach to regulating teacher promotions. This consistency will serve as a continual source of motivation for teachers to exert greater effort in pursuing educational objectives.
2. Ministries of education and principals should also not relent in conducting annual assessment and evaluation of teachers to aid promotion as that would stop them from migrating to other professions to look for greener pastures.

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